

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Scientific Articles

SPOKE N.5 –Industry of Health and Silver Economy

DELIVERABLE 3.3

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	08.01.2026	First Draft	M. Botta, G.B. Giovenzana
0.5	12.01.2026	Additions/Corrections	M. Botta, G.B. Giovenzana
1	15.01.2026	Final Version	M. Botta, G.B. Giovenzana

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

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A) Background and Research Aims

The research activity of RM3 has produced a series of scientific articles, all published in international peer-reviewed journals. The research has focused on the development of innovative molecular probes for diagnostic and therapeutic applications. The work has been organized around various diagnostic and therapeutic techniques that require molecular probes, with particular emphasis on MRI, nuclear medicine, and CT.

B) Scientific articles

List of scientific articles reporting the results of the research of RM3:

- 1) Travagin, F.; Macchia, M.L.; Grell, T.; Bodnár, J.; Baranyai, Z.; Artizzu, F.; Botta, M.; Giovenzana, G.B.: "EHDTA: A Green Approach to Efficient Ln³⁺-Chelators", Dalton Transactions, 2024, 53, 1779-1793. DOI: 10.1039/d3dt03292b
- 2) Versolatto, S.; Boccalon, M.; Guidolin, N.; Travagin, F.; Alessio, E.; Aime, S.; Balducci, G.; Giovenzana, G.B.; Baranyai, Z.: "[Gd(HB-DO3A)]: Equilibrium, Dissociation Kinetic and Structural Differences in a Simple Homolog of [Gd(HP-DO3A)] (Prohance®)", Chemistry-A European Journal, 2024, e202400344. DOI: 10.1002/chem.202400344
- 3) Nucera, A.; Macchia, M.L.; Baranyai, Z.; Carniato, F.; Tei, L.; Ravera, M.; Botta, M.: "Comprehensive Investigation of [Fe(EDTA)]⁻-Functionalized Derivatives and their Supramolecular Adducts with Human Serum Albumin", Inorg. Chem. 2024, 63, 28, 12992–13004. DOI: 10.1021/acs.inorgchem.4c01715
- 4) Macchia, M.L.; Nucera, A.; Ricci, M.; Carniato, F.; Baranyai, Z.; Botta, M.: "Assessing the Impact of Amide Donor Groups on Stability and NMR Relaxation Efficiency of Monohydrated Fe(III) Complexes", Eur. J. Inorg. Chem. 2024, e202400341. DOI: 10.1002/ejic.202400341
- 5) Grattoni, E.; Travagin, F.; Kálmán, F.; Baranyai, Z.; Negri, R.; Carniato, F.; Giovenzana, G.B.; Platas-Iglesias, C.; Botta, M.: "Evaluation of Structurally Related Acyclic Ligands OBETA, EHDTA, and EGTA for Stable Mn²⁺ Complex Formation", Dalton Trans., 2025, 54(1), 376-388. DOI: 10.1039/D4DT02761B
- 6) Tei, L.; Botta, M.; Geraldès, C.F.G.C.: "Beyond Gadolinium: The Potential of Manganese Nanosystems in MRI and Multimodal Imaging Agents", Acta Biomaterialia, 2025, 207, 468-494. DOI: 10.1016/j.actbio.2025.05.058
- 7) Napolitano, R.; Guidolin, N.; Boccalon, M.; Fringuello Mingo, A.; Colombo Serra, S.; Buonsanti, F.; Fretta, R.; Demitri, N.; Bényei, A.; Botta, M.; Giovenzana, G.B.; Tedoldi, F.; Baranyai, Z.: "Chiral Switch of Gadopiclenol: Breaking Conventions in MRI Probe Chemistry", Advanced Science, 2025, 12(14), 2415321. DOI: 10.1002/advs.202415321

- 8) Ricci, M.; Carniato, F.; Corrado, A.; Ferrauto, G.; Di Gregorio, E.; Giovenzana, G.B.; Botta, M.: "Comprehensive relaxometric analysis of Fe(III) coordination polymer nanoparticles for T1-MRI: unravelling the impact of coating on contrast enhancement", *Nanoscale Advances*, 2025, 7, 3792-3802. DOI: 10.1039/D5NA00250H
- 9) Jian, Y.; Cai, Z.; Ding, Y.; Zhang, Z.; Mo, G.; Zhou, X.; Xu, W.; Yan, Z.; Carniato, F.; Ye, F.; Botta, M.; Dai, L.: "New Chiral Pyclyen-Based Gadolinium(III) Complexes: Advancing Stability, Relaxivity, and Water Exchange for Improved Magnetic Resonance Imaging Probes", *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2025, 68, 14254-14270. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jmedchem.4c03122
- 10) Risolo, L.; Ricci, M.; Lalli, D.; Platas-Iglesias, C.; Botta, M.: "Fluoride binding in unlikely partners: the formation of anion-anion complexes with [M(EGTA)]⁻ and [M(OBETA)]⁻ (M = Gd³⁺, Y³⁺)", *Inorganic Chemistry Frontiers*, 2025, 12, 1187-1199. DOI: 10.1039/D4QI02908A
- 11) Hadley, K.A.; Ricci, M.; Hanzevacki, M.; Bernstein, H.; Jayasekera, H.S.; Leney, A.C.; Mulholland, A.J.; Carniato, F.; Botta, M.; Britton, M.M.; Peacock, A.F.A.: "Metallo-coiled Coil Stabilization via Chemical Cross-Linking: Implications for Gd(III)-Based MRI Contrast Agents". *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2025, 147, 42583-42590. DOI: 10.1021/jacs.5c13620
- 12) Salvadori, E.; Lagostina, V.; Ricci, M.; Carniato, F.; Botta, M.; Platas-Iglesias, C.; Chiesa, M.: "From electron spin to relaxivity: a multidisciplinary perspective on first-row transition metal-based MRI probes", *Chemical Science*, 2025, 16, 20631-20646. DOI: 10.1039/D5SC05827A
- 13) Xu, W.; Cai, Z.; Carniato, F.; Lu, Y.; Ye, X.; Xiao, X.; Xu, J.; Mo, G.; Ding, Y.; Jian, Y.; Ruan, X.; Yan, Z.; Ye, F.; Platas-Iglesias, C.; Botta, M.; Dai K.: "Design of Mn(1,4-DO2A) derivatives as stable and inert contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging", *Communications Chemistry*, 2025, 8, 215. DOI: 10.1038/s42004-025-01615-x
- 14) Venucci Merdzo, I.; Travagin, F.; Boccalon, M.; Alessio, E.; Lattuada, L.; Baranyai, Zs.; Giovenzana, G.B.: "TRASUTA: the effect of the structural rigidity of mesocyclic chelating agents on the thermodynamic and kinetic properties of Ga³⁺-complexes", *Inorg. Chem.*, 2024, 63, 12525-12537. DOI: 10.1021/acs.inorgchem.4c01413
- 15) Camorali, S. Nucera, A.; Saccone, M.; Carniato, F.; Botta, M.; Blasi, F.; Baranyai, Z.; Tei, L.: "The timeless relevance of size-match selectivity in macrocyclic Fe(III) complexes", *Inorganic Chemistry Frontiers*, 2025, 12, 4856-4869, DOI: 10.1039/D5QI00431D

C) Conclusion

The planned output of a total of 6 articles has been achieved and largely exceeded, as shown by the list in the document reporting 15 scientific articles published on research products from RM3. The production of scientific articles has focused mainly on MRI probes, to which 14 articles can be attributed compared to the 4 initially expected. The expected scientific article on NM probes reports the results of a study on a potential PET probe. The work carried out on CT probes is not reported in an independent article but is distributed in 2 of the listed publications, which share the research findings on molecular probes potentially usable for multiple diagnostic techniques (MRI and PC-CT).